

Original Research Article

Tracing Mastery Narratives and Recentering a Problem-Solving View of Mathematics

Susan O. Cannon¹
University of Georgia

Erica Warren²
Boys & Girls Clubs of America

Brittney Castanheira³
Mercer University / Denver Public Schools

Merlong Taylor⁴
Mercer University

ABSTRACT: In this paper, we trace qualities of mastery (Singh, 2018) in mathematics education to unearth and work against taken-for-granted ways of being in elementary mathematics classrooms. In order to expose the networked tendrils of mastery thinking, we attend to two data sets. First, we analyze public mathematics narratives through artifacts of K12 schooling, asking, in what ways are qualities of mastery such as splitting, subordination, and the persistence of narratives over time evident (Singh, 2018)? Second, we turn to teachers' reflections on what mathematics is and when they were seen as "good at math" and "bad at math." In our analysis, we aligned their responses to Ernest's (1989) views of mathematics, as reflecting more or less master(full) views of mathematics teaching and learning. We intentionally attune to teachers' narratives of being seen as "good" or "bad" at mathematics as their voices are often silenced or disregarded. We trace how particular and harmful storylines persist as to what counts as mathematics in K12 schooling and how these storylines encase students in hard-to-escape trajectories of failure. We end with proposed counter qualities that align with a problem-solving view of mathematics that centers curiosity, creativity, uncertainty, and joy.

KEYWORDS: *mathematics, mastery narratives, document analysis, teacher education, joy, reciprocity*

¹ Susan O. Cannon (she/her) is an Assistant Professor of Mathematics Education at the University of Georgia. She can be reached via email at cannonso@uga.edu. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3858-3603>

² Erica Warren (she/her) is the Senior Director of Youth Development Programs and Innovations at the Boys & Girls Clubs of America. She can be reached via email at EWarren@BGCA.org.

³ Brittney Castanheira (she/her) is the K-5 Mathematics Manager at Denver Public Schools. She can be reached via email at b_castanheira@dpsk12.net. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4440-9364>

⁴ Merlong Taylor (she/her) is a doctoral candidate at Mercer University. She can be reached via email at merlongtaylor@gmail.com. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4833-4643>

Although the term mastery has over the decades been employed at a casual distance from its violent colonial origins, its use continues to covertly and subtly shape our engagement with mathematics and one another (Wozolek, 2020). In this paper we consider how we might disrupt and reimagine mathematics classrooms. While our experiences and the research have shown that unraveling the structures and practices in schools that uphold mastery narratives and perpetuate the good at math/bad at math binary are difficult to undermine, we put forward joy, creativity, and curiosity as counter movements that might disrupt. Sharpe (2016) employs the wake, the disturbance of water created by a ship's passing, as a metaphor to describe the enduring impact of slavery on black life. Similarly, the wake of mastery's historical associations is important to acknowledge. We begin with an exploration of good at math/bad at math.

From Georgia, With Love

We, the four of us, are mothers, teachers, daughters, educators, artists, feminists, and we are academic mothers who are caught in the unattainable pursuit of the “good life” (Jenkins et al., 2023). Susan and Brittney are both white cis-gendered woman and teacher educators. Susan taught elementary and middle school mathematics and science in Atlanta area public schools for 13 years before transitioning to academia. Brittney taught elementary school, was a tenure-track professor, and now serves as a district mathematics leader. Erica and Merlong are both Black cis-gendered women who worked in schools as teachers and academic coaches of new and veteran teachers. Merlong's experience is in elementary education, while Erica's is in middle school mathematics. At the time we wrote this paper, we all lived in Georgia.

Collectively, our work in schools spanned the eras of No Child Left Behind, Race to the Top, Adequate Yearly Progress, Common Core, the Covid-19 Pandemic, the Reading Wars, and Divisive Concepts legislation. The legislation, movements, and events over this 20-plus-year span have pointed U.S. society and schools to pursue mastery and have deepened our investment in qualities of mastery that we outline below. As teacher-educators and coaches we have found ourselves caught in a cloud that blurs the violent nature of mastery through bureaucratic, political, and social investments in progress as a wholly public good. Our experiences offer many examples that the wake of mastery ripples into the present day. For example, as an instructional coach, Erica engaged in the promotion of the mastery narrative of mathematics, pushing the gradual release (I do, we do, you do) model of instruction and the analysis of testing data to split children into tiers of mastery because that is what the job required. Susan entered Atlanta Public Schools in the aftermath of the 2009 cheating scandal (Staff reports, 2015) and experienced strict surveillance of students and teachers. She was a middle school graduation coach in a school with a population of students that were 99% Black and was taught to target “bubble kids” for whom her efforts would result in increases in the school's CCRPI⁵ score. After five years, she transitioned to a school promising a more humane pedagogy, but within years, she found herself promoting an “academic growth period,” a euphemism for an instructional period involving the sorting and subordinating of students with lower test scores for remediation, while students who had mastered topics were offered enrichment. Even when we recognize the misguided investment in mastery as antithetical

⁵ College and Career Ready Performance Index is “is Georgia's annual tool for measuring how well its schools, districts, and the state itself are preparing students for the next educational level. It provides a comprehensive roadmap to help educators, parents, and community members promote and improve college and career readiness for all students. The CCRPI includes five main components each scored on a scale of 0 to 100: Content Mastery, Progress, Closing Gaps, Readiness, and Graduation Rate (high school only). The CCRPI also reports other information, such as the performance of student subgroups, school climate, and financial efficiency status.” (GADOE, 2023a)

to our aims of joy and justice in education, it is nearly impossible to propel ourselves and others in another direction. The work of imagining what exists outside of mastery is often set aside because the waves of testing, data analysis, personalized learning platforms, and other seemingly innocuous school practices thrash against us at such a pace and force that we fight to simply stay afloat.

The educational industrial complex which includes testing and curriculum companies like Pearson, policymakers, and philanthropists is upholding mastery views of mathematics (Attick & Boyles, 2016; Desai, 2015). There has been an influx of mandated and prescribed curricula in elementary mathematics classrooms including *gradual release*—I do, we do, you do—instructional strategies (Auslander et al., 2023; Fisher & Frey, 2021; García & DeNicolo, 2019; Skilton-Sylvester, 2020) and an increase in individualized computer-based learning (Brezovszky et al., 2019; Chu et al., 2021) all proclaiming to *fix* students and help them catch up. The former prescribes a teaching method that bends toward defining algorithmic memorization and replication as mathematics mastery. The latter is held up as a savior (Georgia Partnership for Excellence in Education, 2021) to the learning loss that parents and educators are told threatens children’s futures (e.g., Baumgaertner, 2023; Mervosh, 2022). These interactions between students and algorithms cast them as proficient or not and advise quick fixes for their deficits. These technological splits are replicated in classrooms as students deemed proficient are split into advanced mathematics classes, away from those whose scores were “below mastery.” We are particularly concerned about the ways that the groupings of testing software are presented as natural, normal, and true in their black and white assurances and red-yellow-green sortings.

Whether done through teacher-created or technology-mediated assessment, these sortings reward particular types of mathematical knowledge as they create trajectories into careers and livelihoods rich with, or cut off from the rewards of demonstrations of mathematical mastery (Oehrlein, 2009; Thomas & Zhang, 2005). Teachers are under immense pressure to help their students achieve not only progress but mastery in mathematics while recognizing that what the state and testing companies recognize as mastery might not help their students to feel like (or be) capable and competent mathematicians. The number of tested mathematics concepts in K-12 classrooms requires an attention to progress and movement through the curriculum that precludes a focus on deep exploration of mathematical ideas. Yet, the timing of state tests a month or more before the end of the school year suggests that students *should* be able to achieve mastery quickly and at roughly the same pace as their peers. When students fail to master all or even most of the content by the testing date, they are sometimes punished for their deviance from *normal* with remedial or intervention coursework that may take the place of exploratory classes, like art or music (Travis, 2008; Dang, 2007). In 2024, 56% of Georgia eighth graders scored below proficient on the Milestones state assessment (GADOE, 2023b), an indication that failure is in fact *normal*. The urgency around correcting the perceived learning loss due to school disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic accentuates the idea that mathematics content should be encapsulated and taken regularly to prevent failure for students, teachers, and schools. We push back against these linear and confined learning trajectories and the profit-focused curricula and interventions that benefit from them (Attick & Boyles, 2016; Cannon et al., In press). Without grappling with the violent history and the present instantiations of mastery, we have no hope of reframing school mathematics.

Who Gets to Be Good at Math...

*I feel that I am good at mathematics. It depends on the math that is being done. Mathematics to me is **straightforward for the most part. You get an answer, and that is it.** Sure there are different ways of getting to the answer, but **you get the same answer.** (Olivia)*

*My teacher would sit the students that did the worst on an assignment in the front of the class. **I had to sit in the front of the class one time and was mortified and embarrassed. I hated that class.** I felt that was not helpful to any students. The teacher was not doing anyone a favor by embarrassing students. This was only fueling their dislike for math and, quite frankly, her. (Avery)*

Larnell (2019) argued mathematical proficiency has been narrowly defined as a “collection of attributes required for one to be regarded as a viable participant in mathematics education” (p. 130). As these two quotes demonstrate, what counts as mathematics and who is seen as good or bad at mathematics are entangled in classroom practices and personal experiences. We began this project with a curiosity about the prevalence of elementary teachers in our undergraduate and graduate mathematics methods courses who proclaimed that they were “bad at math.” We wondered how these subjectivities developed and persisted and how we might invite teachers to uncover and reconsider the norms and classroom practices that uphold “bad at math” narratives and stifle children’s creativity, curiosity, and joy. In this section, we begin by elaborating

Drawing on Ahmed’s (2013) idea that discomfort signals the need for criticality, Singh (2018) suggests that “discomfort allows us to pose the question of why some bodies can and cannot fit comfortably within particular spaces” (p. 151). Many teachers we have worked with across our various contexts grapple with a historicized discomfort and anxiety with mathematics. Thus, we engage in their stories of being seen as good at math or bad at math both to understand “where we [and they] know from” (McKittrick, 2021), and to read their and our histories as entangled in pervasive mastery discourses. Singh (2018) advises that “approaching these constitutive narratives with vulnerability—with a willingness to engage that which we have wished to avoid, and in doing so be crafted anew—can be a world-making practice through which we become other to ourselves” (p. 109).

As the first quote above highlights, whether a student can “feel that I am good at mathematics... depends on the math being done.” In other words, good at math/bad at math subjectivities are entangled with *what counts as mathematics in schools*. In order to explore the teachers’ views of mathematics and how public mathematics narratives are entangled with them, we draw on Ernest’s (1989) framework for the views on the nature of mathematics as instrumentalist, Platonist, or problem solving. School mathematics tends toward instrumentalist views, especially with the prevalence of high-stakes testing and gradual release—I do, we do, you do—pedagogical imperatives. These repeat-after-me teaching strategies encapsulate mathematics as a thing to be practiced and perfected, what the teacher above describes as “straightforward for the most part. You get an answer and that’s it.” Instrumentalist, or procedural, mathematics upholds the qualities of mastery that rely on stable binaries and rigid conceptions as to what counts as right or wrong. In contrast, a problem-solving view upholds mathematics as an open, creative, and joyful endeavor with many possible outcomes and pathways. Returning to the quotes above, Avery is singled out for her performance on a single assignment, split off and subordinated from her peers who got more answers correct on the assessment. Her performances did not fit the normative mathematical identity of the classroom, so she was seen as bad at math. The normative identity is an agreed upon, though negotiated, way of being in the classroom.

The research has shown that there is hope for recalibrating what counts as good and bad at math. In an ecological study of one sixth grade teacher's classroom, Ruef (2021) analyzed the teacher's attempts to shift normative mathematics identity over the course of a school year. "Good-at-math" normative identities that are narrowly defined "gate opportunities to learn" (p. 154). Through bids, including explicit requests, verbal cues, assignment of roles in group work, and recognition of student thinking, and negotiations, Ruef shared how the teacher and students made and adhered to new agreements that allowed a shift in what and who got counted as good at math. Bids consist of implicit or explicit requests for action. Requests for action that are consistently taken up within a classroom community become obligations that indicate mathematical competence. At the beginning of the school year, the students' agreed upon obligations for good-at-math included compliance, smartness, good grades, quickness and attentiveness. Through accepting alternative bids offered by the teacher, such as taking risks and making sure everyone on a team understood the mathematics, the obligations changed throughout the year. By March, students included making mistakes, explaining well, presenting one's thinking, and being helpful as markers of "good at math." Ruef's case supports the possibility of a reimagining and remaking of "good-at-mathematics" for teachers and students. The teacher's ways of being otherwise with her students upset the previously socially constructed normative identity of mathematical competence.

While individual teachers, as in the example above, may (and do) push back against narratives of mastery in mathematics, individual action is not enough. In a study of four urban high school mathematics teachers, Louie (2017) found that what she called a culture of exclusion "maintained a significant presence" (p. 498) in the teachers' classrooms even though the teachers were explicitly engaged in professional development focused on advancing equity. She describes the exclusionary framing as "the rote practice frame" where "mathematics is a fixed body of knowledge to be absorbed and practiced" and "correctness is paramount" (Louie, 2017, p. 496). The teachers in her study attempted to enact more inclusive framings of mathematics and mathematical ability; however, the dominant culture of the exclusionary frame interfered with their attempts. She concluded that the field of mathematics education needs to view exclusionary practices "as a cultural and not solely an individual phenomenon" (p. 516). As we will demonstrate in our section on mastery narratives in school contexts, teachers are bombarded with framings of students that position them as lacking, behind, and in need of catching up. These frames are so prevalent that they slip into the atmosphere and go unquestioned.

Mastery, according to Singh, is everywhere—"ubiquitous, reproductive, and beyond enumeration, mastery appears inescapable," and its apparent inescapability is what draws Singh to attend to it, and seek out other "modes of relational being" (p. 1). Three qualities of mastery undergird Singh's (2018) tracing—splitting, subordination, and narratives over time. These qualities offer a useful framework, which we will explain below, to attend to the ways that policies and practices in mathematics education, position students and teachers in problematic ways. In this manuscript, across the data sources presented, we grapple with the questions: Where are the qualities of mastery showing up or escaping notice in and around mathematics classrooms? What kinds of communities build and sustain teachers and researchers in transforming a culture of exclusion? What bids and negotiations might foster more joyful, curious, and creative mathematical classrooms? We do not, yet, have the answers to these questions, but center them to disrupt taken-for-granted ways of being and doing mathematics and mathematics education research. We begin by examining the context that fosters and supports the prevalence of mastery narratives in schools.

The Tie that Binds: Mastery, the Pursuit of Progress, and Instrumentalist Mathematics

Mathematics education is bound to ideas of progress that perpetuate good at math/bad at math narratives and is tethered to the qualities of mastery that Singh (2018) outlined. These narratives rely on and are reinforced by a belief in mathematics as procedural and instrumentalist (Ernest, 1989). A belief that, as Ernest (2023) argued, is normalized through power-imbalanced teacher-student relationships and attached to the ordered and patterned discipline of, especially, early mathematics. We draw attention to this connection between the pursuit of progress and the nature of mathematics to consider how other ideas about the nature of mathematics might work the ground in the field of mathematics education to create possibilities for other ways of being/doing mathematics. Figure 1 articulates a master(full) mathematics and the ways that Singh’s and Ernest’s tenants are aligned. Splitting, subordination, and narrative over time are supported, upheld, and made possible through instrumentalist, and Platonist views of mathematics. Next, we outline the qualities of mastery before connecting those qualities to the pursuit of progress and instrumentalist mathematics.

Fig. 1. Qualities of mastery and views of mathematics

Qualities of Mastery⁶

According to Julietta Singh’s (2018) explorations in *Unthinking Mastery*, mastery is a relational orientation between a subject and the world whereby the world, in whole or in part, is viewed as property, experienced as subordinate, and made to yield to the subject and its progeny. Singh outlined three qualities of mastery: splitting, subordination, and narrative over time. Splitting creates boundaries and divisions. Once splitting is achieved, a person or a thing can then be placed on one side or the other of the boundary that the split creates.

school real-world

student teacher

low high

unmotivated gifted

⁶ In this section, we provoke a diffractive reading—“an intra-action between texts that brings new texts into being” (Hepler et al., 2019, p. 143). We juxtapose our theoretical writings and descriptions of mastery with language from K12 schools, educational technology, policy manuals, and positions to draw out questions and insights rather than answers. The texts shift positions throughout the next several sections to re-and dis-orient (Ahmed, 2006) the reader. We also use this section to stretch the boundaries of what can count as “sensible” academic writing (Cannon & Holbrook, 2020).

Splitting is a foundational quality of mastery and is “a way of estranging the mastered object from its previous state of being” (p. 10) and involves “carving a boundary or an infliction of mutilation—or, often, both at the same time” (p. 12). We see this in schools in particular in how students are grouped into those who have “met the standard” or not, and even in the casual ways that some teachers speak about their “high fliers” and “low babies.” Splitting allows the second quality of mastery that Singh (2018) traced—subordination—to take place. Singh connected splitting and subordination, stating: “The splitting that is inherent to mastery, the fracturing that confirms and inaugurates it, and the ongoing practices of subordination that drive it forward are inescapable in the foundational thinking of the subject of modern political thought” (p. 13). Once groups have been split, mastery narratives then subordinate “what is on one side of a border to the power of what is on the other” (p. 13). The “good at math” students are on one side (of the classroom, or the school, or the bulletin board showing math fact progression) and the “bad at math” students are on the other.

The final quality of mastery that Singh discussed is narrative over time. While splitting and subordination matter in the moment, it is these positionings’ persistence over time that cements the binary. Singh described this quality of mastery as “a struggle that must unfold in time and come to be recognized as permanent” (p. 14). In other words, narrative helps mastery become normalized so that imagining relations outside of splitting and subordination becomes difficult. The narratives that instantiate the subjectivities around mathematics take on this permanence.

Here is where the participants’ reflections about times that they have been seen as “good at math” and “bad at math” come into our argument. As we have listened and looked across the hundreds of stories we have heard over the years, as teachers, parents, mothers, the refrain, “I’m not good at math” resonates across contexts. It clings, recirculates, and is passed on as an inheritance. Parents walked into our mathematics classrooms to discuss their child’s progress. “I’m not good at math, she gets it from me.” Of course, parents’ narratives are but one source that can cement these stories in time, and parents, most likely, learned this *truth* about themselves from their experiences in K12 environments. So, we are interested in the stories that elementary teachers carry with them about their own experiences with mathematics, what they might indicate mathematics *is*, and how those reflections interact with public discourses in schools.

According to Singh’s (2018) argument, the “bad at math student” once recognized as such through evidence of slowness, low test scores, or the perception of others is subordinated

career-track college bound

real-world

school

teacher

student

high

low

gifted

unmotivated

college bound

career-track

“A new course blending option has been made available for advanced learners that includes Enhanced Algebra and AP Precalculus” (GADOE, 2023a, Slide 17)

through the language of mastery (i.e., “below mastery”), and their subordination is taken up as a permanent condition. Despite the moment-in-time-ness of one’s subordination, public and authoritative affirmations of one’s goodness or badness at math permeate the identity constructions of young mathematicians (Skultety et al, 2023; Soares 2022). Students who are tracked into “bad at math” trajectories tend to persist in those trajectories. Even though states such as Georgia claim to provide students with “multiple on-ramps and off-ramps as they matriculate through the secondary grade levels” (GADOE, 2023a, Slide 11), the likelihood of students without substantial support using the on-ramps that the “opportunities for all” (GADOE, 2023a, slide 1) pathways outline require students to have a belief that they can be “good at math.” Furthermore, the placement of students into lower tracks is both racialized and gendered (Francis & Darity, 2021; Martin et al., 2019). The qualities of mastery—the splitting and subordinating that over time persist as a narrative of “good at math”—lend to subsequent placement into advanced or accelerated tracks, which in turn make disproportionate representations in these courses seem normal and natural (Hendield, 2011; Joseph et al., 2019; Van Ryzin & Vincent, 2017). This is not to say, necessarily, that these narratives of mastery are intentionally and individually deployed, as Singh (2018) points out at times, “we engage unthinkingly in masterful acts that we firmly believe to be harmless, benevolent, or even works of art” (p. 174). All the more reason to engage in a “detailed and sustained examination of mastery” (p. 174).

Mastery, Instrumentalist Views, and the Pursuit of Progress

“The standards are presented through a logical progression and provide detailed information as students work toward master of the key competencies/ standards of the grade level/course” (GADOE, 2023a, slide 4)

“The standards presented for each grade level and course represent the ultimate expectation for mastery at each grade level

To examine the ways qualities of mastery such as splitting, subordination, and the persistence of narratives over time are evident in public documents related to mathematics and to explore how views of mathematics are aligned with teachers’ narratives, we employ and draw connections across three theoretical frameworks: Singh’s (2018) qualities of mastery and Ernest’s (1989) views of mathematics (See Figure 1), and Llewellyn’s (2016) theoretical paper about the pursuit of progress in mathematics education. To begin to understand the pervasiveness of the good at math/bad at math binary, we acknowledge the connection between mathematics, success, and progress. Llewellyn (2016) argued that mathematics education is “unequivocally committed to straightforward progress” (p. 308) and that mathematics education adheres its forward momentum to progress writ large in society. In other words, progress is necessary for success in mathematics education and is tied to success in society. The attachment to progress and the ideas necessary to measure our distance from it, according to

for each big idea” (GADOE, 2023a, Slide 4)

“Students master levels by answering 40 questions correctly within their mastery time goal. The teacher can adjust mastery time goals per student and per level to provide the most appropriate challenge for each student. Students can challenge their best times.” (Math Facts in a Flash, pg. 3)

“Is she a high flier or a low baby?”

“Well, what’s her MAP score?”

“How did she do on the GA Milestones?”

“We don’t do those tests anymore.”

“How do you know who they are?”

“We listen to them. We see how they are in the world, who they are in community.”

“That’s not reliable!!”

“The testing companies say we need data. We can’t trust ourselves.”

“Tell me, why?”

Llewellyn, require that “we fabricate what it is to be successful at mathematics and hence what the ‘mathematical child’ should be” (p. 300). To return to our argument above, the pursuit of progress requires a clear delineation between good at math and bad at math and Ernest’s (1989) instrumentalist views. The instrumentalist view of mathematics elevates the collection of mathematical rules used to solve practical problems, and dismisses abstract notions that mathematics might say something about the world. Recognizing and defining what the mathematical child is or is not (through right/wrong answers) is a process of splitting. The ideal mathematical child allows the measurement of progress against a norm. The mathematical child is not only a fabrication, but one that is unnecessarily and egregiously applied to children at the earliest signs of the presence or lack of ‘natural’ talent.

Nonetheless, this construction of the ideal mathematical child allows and upholds the binary of good at math/bad at math. Once splitting has occurred, bad at math students are subordinated to good at math students. Llewellyn suggested that “the person who more easily succeeds at mathematics in school is created by the discourses that circulate within mathematics education” (p. 300). The instrumentalist discourse that faster is better, which is reinforced by timed fact tests, for example, produces fluency as a characteristic of good at math, and in turn rewards students who are already fluent. In other words, the good at math student is produced through socio-political discourse and experiences material consequences that perpetuate and reward their alignment with good at math characteristics. Good at math students (and teachers) become invested in the good at math narratives that uphold their position and reinforce those narratives and the maintenance of their dominant positions (de Freitas, 2008). Llewellyn described students who do not easily fit into these normalized, measurable, and linear characteristics as “messy” (p. 300) and “deviant” (p. 310). These labels also adhere and persist within the confines of school especially with easy to measure characteristics (such as fluency).

Fluency is easily counted, perceived, and measured, and the pursuit of progress requires an advancement from here/now to there/then and a measurable and positive difference between those times/spaces. In other words, in order to see the progress of society/schools, students are compared on knowledges that are easily measured. The ease of measurement, not the importance of

⁷ All quotes without attributions are drawn for the authors’ combined years of listening in schools and reflect either things we have heard reverberating over and over, in the first sections, or imagined things we would like to hear in schools, in the final sections.

“What are schools for? What are teachers for?” the knowledge for the child or society, determines the privilege and the splitting and subordination that follows.

“Why does that matter?”

“We need to know who’s who?”

Llewellyn’s (2016) pursuit of progress and Ernest’s views of mathematics cohere as a tool to assist in our “detailed and sustained examination of mastery” (Singh, 2017, p. 174). Now we turn to explore the alignment between Singh’s qualities of mastery (2017) and Ernest’s (1989) framework classifying views of the nature of mathematics.

A Framework for Teacher Beliefs about the Nature of Mathematics

Ernest (1989) outlined three forms of beliefs which, importantly given our interest in Singh’s work, he described as “a tentative attempt to specify the essential knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes of the mathematics teacher” (p. 14). According to Ernest, the knowledges, beliefs, and attitudes that teachers bring to the classroom influence the teacher’s mathematics instruction, and subsequently, the students’ beliefs about mathematics. Ernest pointed out that teachers may simultaneously hold parts of more than one of the views and that beliefs may be implicitly rather than explicitly held. In other words, while the categories are helpful in thinking about teacher beliefs, a teacher’s beliefs are dynamic, and the categories cannot contain all the perspectives of teachers. As we work with these seemingly discrete categories, we think of them along a continuum with no clear boundaries between categories and remember that the model is tentative. In this paper, we focus on teachers’ beliefs about the nature of mathematics.

Within the conception of the nature of mathematics, Ernest (1989) described three perspectives. The first is a “dynamic, problem-driven view of mathematics as a continually expanding field of human inquiry” (p. 21) where mathematics is never finished and is open to revision. He named this the problem-solving view. The second, the Platonist view, is the view that mathematics is a static body of knowledge, “a monolith, a static immutable product” (p. 21). Finally, in the instrumentalist view, mathematics is a set of rules, facts, and procedures. Ernest’s three views of mathematics can be placed on a continuum where one side represents a more dynamic view of mathematics and the other represents a less dynamic view. Along this continuum, the problem-solving view would be dynamic and the instrumentalist view would be less dynamic. An instrumentalist view of mathematics allows Singh’s qualities of mastery to flourish. See figure 1. In other words, an instrumentalist view of mathematics aligns with either-or thinking and allows easy splitting.

math is.....

open to revision?

building on student’s thinking?

centering students as creators of mathematics?

focusing on structure?

understanding the laws of number?

knowing the central and unifying concepts of mathematics?

doing the procedure, procedure, procedure?

getting back to basics?

just the facts, ma’am!

It was what it was....

I do

The problem-solving view, however, presents a challenge to the project of schooling as it makes processes of splitting and subordination cumbersome. A mathematics that is open to revision is difficult to measure using traditional forms of assessment. The problem-solving view calls into question the rigid ways that schools have defined mastery as the percentage of correct responses. If mathematics is, as the problem-solving view holds, about the various ways mathematical thinking helps individuals and communities to solve everyday and novel problems, it would seem, then, that the quotidian mathematical relations that occur in classrooms and outside of school stand in stark contrast to the correct responses on a computer based assessment, which allow us to track a student's ability to perform the basic operations, but tell us nothing about a child's relationship to mathematics in their world.

Given Ernest's three types of beliefs about the nature of mathematics and Singh's urging toward decolonizing mastery, this study explores documents that reflect the socio-political context within which teachers are working and elementary mathematics teachers' reflections about mathematics to better understand the ways teachers are at once tethered to mastery narratives and trying to escape these ways of being. Furthermore, we seek to draw connections between mastery narratives and the potential of otherwise futures.

Data Sources and Analysis

In order to explore the ways that the qualities of mastery (Singh, 2018) and Ernest's (1989) conceptions of mathematics reverberate, we look to two sources of data. First, we conducted a document analysis (Prior, 2003) of public documents including a Georgia Milestones (the state-wide performance assessment in Georgia) assessment report, individualized learning platforms, and other documents and texts that circulate in elementary mathematics education. Second, we analyzed the written reflections of three cohorts of inservice elementary school teachers enrolled in a K5 Mathematics endorsement certification program in Georgia.

In our document analysis of the websites and performance report, we looked for evidence of the qualities of mastery, pursuit of progress, and belief in the nature of mathematics in the text and graphical representations displayed. We asked ourselves where and how splitting, subordination, and narrative over time were reflected in the ways that the programs described their purpose.

In addition to our analysis of these documents, we collected a single written reflection from three cohorts of in-service teachers beginning in 2020 and ending in the Fall of 2022. 31 reflections were collected via a learning management system as a part of coursework in the second or third week of a 36-week endorsement. We asked teachers enrolled to reflect on the following questions as a part of their first assignment in their coursework:

1. How would you define mathematics to someone who does not know anything about it?
2. What counts as mathematical knowledge? Who gets to decide?
3. How have you been seen by others (or yourself) as "good" or "bad" at mathematics?

The research team coded the responses using the qualitative management software, Dedoose.

In our framework, these reflections document the teachers' views of the nature of mathematics that persist over time (Singh, 2018) in the memories of teachers as to the splitting between "good at math" and "bad at math" and the subsequent subordination(s). Three research team members utilized open coding to analyze the teachers' narratives. Initial codes were then collapsed through conversation amongst the team members. All reflections were coded by at least two members of the research team. The final list of codes included: "good at math" with nine child codes, "bad at math" with eight child codes (see the right-hand column for a listing of child codes). After the initial coding, we did an additional round of elaborative coding (Saldaña, 2016, p. 255) using Paul Ernest's (1989) framework around the nature of mathematics. We coded excerpts of data as:

1. Instrumentalist (math is a set of rules and procedures)
2. Platonist (math is a unified unchanging body of knowledge)
3. Problem-solving (math is person-made creation that is continually expanding)

Following Singh (2018), we attempted a vulnerable reading of the teachers' reflections and data excerpts focusing on our questions: Where are the qualities of mastery showing up or escaping notice in and around mathematics classrooms? What kinds of communities might build and sustain teachers and researchers in transforming a culture of exclusion? What bids and negotiations might foster more joyful, curious, and creative mathematical classrooms? Singh described vulnerable reading as "an open, continuous, practice that resists foreclosures by remaining unremittingly susceptible to new world configurations that reading texts- literary, artistic, philosophical, and political-can begin to produce" (p. 22). While we might have considered the written reflections from the teachers in isolation, instead we intentionally put them into conversation with the mastery narratives pervasive in school contexts and curricula laid out above. In addition, in the side columns we encourage a diffractive reading (Hepler et al., 2019) across texts allowing the political, artistic, and literary to interrupt and reorient. In diffractive reading, the goal is not a truth about a particular context or group of participants, but insights into the difference *difference* might make (Cannon,

*Good at Math**...good teacher**...didn't need help**...conceptual understanding**...procedural fluency**...fast**...joy**...thinking style or aptitude**...perception of others**...race/identity**Bad at Math**bad teacher**needed help**didn't understand conceptual**only procedures**sssssllllllloooooomwwww*

2022). By attending to the intricacies of the knowledge-making apparatus, might we come to understand how these narratives are produced and persist? Put another way, how might our attending to mastery narratives and reading them across and with the pursuit of progress (Llewellyn, 2016) and Ernest’s (1989) framework of mathematics provide insights and questions that might allow us to tell different stories and live different lives (Haraway, 2016)?

so slow

public humiliation

thinking style

labeled/tracked

Narratives of Educational and Technological Splits

We begin with the analysis of department of education documents, adaptive testing, and personalized learning software used in elementary school contexts, and the Georgia Milestones Assessment report. These are some of the messages, discourses, and narratives that permeate elementary teachers’ day to day interactions in schools.

When we considered adaptive testing and personalized learning software in relation to the qualities of mastery, we found that the products and platforms upheld splitting and subordination. In terms of narrative over time, they provided suggestions to support students’ growth over time, suggesting the possibility of movement from one position to another. Yet, the business model of these testing agencies depends on students’ persistent un-mastery (Attick & Boyles, 2016).

In reviewing the ways that the products described their purpose, each aligned to a pursuit of progress and proclaimed that their data was a legitimate and accurate way to assess what students know. iReady, a program that assesses student reading and prescribes a learning path that if followed, will move a child closer to mastery, describes their products as a means to “see exactly where your students are” (Curriculum Associates, 2023, para. 2); MAP, a norm-referenced assessment system, claimed that their assessments “reduce the manual work of differentiating math instruction” (NWEA, 2023, para. 2); and DRC Beacon, an adaptive and interim testing program provided to all schools in Georgia by the GaDOE, advertises that the program will “help students stay on track” in ELA and Math (Data Recognition Corporation, 2023, para. 2).

As a part of fulfilling these promises, each program relies on splitting. They sort rosters of students automatically for teachers into categories based on technology-mediated interactions. The MAP website asserts to teachers that it is “helping you make decisions with

Fig. 2. Proficient Learner

My daughter scored in the 94 PR in 4th grade and the 91PR in the 5th grade. The MAP parent report highlighted this

confidence” (The MAP Suite, para 3) iReady, Beacon, and MAP respectively subordinate as follows: Above Grade Level, On grade Level, One Grade Level Below, Two Grade Levels Below, Three or More Grade Levels Below; Prepared, Near target, Support needed; Low, Average, High, with the higher categories labeled in green and the lower levels blanketed in cautionary red. Thus, the students who do not test as well as a norm-referenced peer on instrumentalist mathematics are subordinated to those who do.

In addition to the splitting and subordination, these platforms proclaim to be infallible measures of knowledge. In “A Family Guide to MAP Growth,” the company asserts that MAP can “accurately measure what students know, regardless of their grade level. It also measures growth over time, allowing you to track your child’s progress throughout the school year” (NWEA, 2022, p. 1). The document states, “RIT scale precisely measures student performance, regardless of whether they’re performing on, above, or below grade level”(p. 1). These assertions of accuracy and precision about a child’s knowledge based on one test mislead teachers and parents that the results are not to be questioned or taken up with other sources of data.

Once determined, the performance levels are characterized as qualities of the learners (Proficient Learner, Figure 2), rather than assigned to the score or performance (Proficient Score). The score report classifies the type of learner, rather than the quality of learning and in doing so encourages educators, students, and their families to take up the narrative that learning is an independent endeavor toward mastery. Performance on one test on one day marks each student as deficient or not and those narratives persist over time. These characterizations help shift single demonstrations of mathematical knowledge into more permanent good/bad at math narratives. While the report is derived from the student’s performance on one or two days of testing, the score slips from characterizing the performance to characterizing the person to whom it is connected. This slippage from the test score as evidence of learning to an indication of who the student *is* has material consequences for the student, teacher, and family. In addition, as a school’s average mathematics mastery rolls into school report card scores, student scores coalesce into determinations of whether a community is a desirable place to live and raise a family. The category becomes a characteristic of the student with associated actions in response (i.e., remediate, monitor, accelerate). The focus on individualism is evident across discourses. We see it in the language of the learning platforms designed to support students on their “individual paths to success” (i-Ready) and to allow students to “individually see their progress and be inspired to take charge of their own learning” (MAP). Competition and keeping up are valued above cooperation and collaboration.

loss and provided a warning that this was low growth and highlighted it in red. My daughter was anxious about this. She was reading (according to MAP better than 90% of the students, yet received the messaging that that was not enough).
Susan

“Did everyone hear Anita’s idea? Anita, can you say that again so everyone can hear?”

“What do you think that might look like if we represented it?”

“Do you think that would work in all cases? Chat with your neighbors and let me know what you think.”

“Pearson has aggressive lobbyists, top-notch marketing and a highly skilled sales team.” (Simon, 2015)

“The \$1 billion-a-year nonprofit [ETS] pays its directors for-profit salaries. Outgoing president Kurt Landgraf received \$1.3 million in total compensation in 2013.” (Strauss, 2015)

“Joy is fun and celebratory, yet it is not only about having fun and celebrating... It is also the embodiment of, learning of, and practice of love of self and humanity, and care for and help for humanity and the earth. Joy encompasses happiness/smiles, truth, beauty, aesthetics, art, wonder, personal

In addition to identifying the qualities of mastery in these programs with which many teachers interact on a daily or weekly basis, all Georgia teachers and parents receive Georgia Milestone Assessment reports describing their students' progress at the end of the school year. Figure 3 in the right-hand column shows a sample Georgia Milestones assessment performance report issued to teachers and students' families. A Georgia Department of Education document (2023) explained the domain mastery achievement levels' purpose is to "describe student mastery and command of the knowledge and skills" and to "succinctly describe how much mastery a student has" (para. 1). The Georgia Milestones Assessment splits student performance into four levels: Beginning, Developing, Proficient, and Distinguished. Each level is differentiated by how completely the learner has demonstrated proficiency from not yet demonstrated, partially demonstrated, proficiency, and advanced proficiency. Connected to these levels are recommendations. Beginning learners "need substantial academic support to be prepared for the next grade level or course and to be on track for college and career readiness" (para. 3) while developing learners "need additional academic support" (para. 4), proficient learners, "are prepared" (para. 5) and distinguished learners "are well prepared" (para. 6). The learners who "need additional" or "substantial" academic support are called out as not being "on track" for college and career readiness, a trajectory which the state applies to pupils as young as eight years old. These predictions and assertions are dangerous examples of the "narrative over time" quality of mastery and send messages to students, parents, and teachers about who children will become.

fulfillment, and solutions to the social problems of the world." (Muhammad, 2023, p. 70)

"That was beautiful, I'd never thought of it that way before."

Fig. 3. Levels and Actions

Splitting Mathematical Subjects

The second source of data that we considered were reflections from three cohorts of inservice teachers in Georgia. For each teacher's reflection, we divided the text into excerpts. The excerpts were bound by changes in topic, new paragraphs, or significant changes in tone. While the reflections provided answers to the questions above, when reading the excerpts, the research team coded each excerpt for the view of mathematics that the excerpts reflected (Instrumentalist, Platonic, or Problem-Solving View). Ernest (2023) connects the dots between the instrumentalist and Platonist views and mastery narratives in mathematics explaining that "imperatives become inscribed in mathematical objects and are seen as implicitly within them, rather than as the deontic (normative) rules that regulate their possible uses" (p. 11). In other words, the culture of mathematics reinforces instrumentalist and Platonist views of mathematics that privilege following prescribed rules. In the next section, we present data from teacher reflections. First, we share data excerpts aligned to beliefs about the nature of mathematics, then we follow with resonances of mastery narratives in those reflections.

Beliefs about the Nature of Mathematics

After coding the excerpts, we found that the majority (75 out of 104) of excerpts reflected instrumentalist views of mathematics, characterized by participants' defining (1) mathematics as a set of steps to follow and (2) mathematical knowledge as the successful completion of a series of steps without mistakes. A smaller percentage of excerpts (18 out of 104) seemed to hold Platonist

views of mathematics, characterized by (1) expanding “good at math” to include playing with numbers beyond the standard algorithms, and (2) extending mathematics outside of the classroom to include real-world problem-solving. The excerpts characterized as Platonist maintained that mathematics is factual and often reduced to a single correct answer. Therefore, these experts still reflect a view that mathematics is can be mastered, albeit through less rigid processes. We noted a problem-solving view in 11 of 104 excerpts where participants alluded to problem-solving skills beyond algorithmic steps leading to a single answer, but none of these could be classified as explicitly problem-solving as the responses remained tethered to mastery narratives of speed, accuracy, and right/wrong thinking.

Instrumentalist belief

When the teachers were asked what counts as mathematical knowledge, many excerpts referenced a belief that understanding operations and steps were critical to mathematical knowledge. The quote below from a participant is representative of the types of reflections that we classified as instrumentalist:

From elementary school through most of high school, I can remember people telling me I was good at math. While I could not solve some problems as fast as others, math always seemed to come to me naturally. However, looking back at it I feel like I was good at math because memorization was something that I could do easily.

The teacher’s reflection on the importance of speed, which she presents as counter-evidence to being labeled as good at math, and memorization, which ultimately landed her in the “good at math” category aligns with Ernest’s (1989) instrumentalist belief in the nature of mathematics.

Another teacher described mathematical knowledge as “the ability to make sense of numbers, and seamlessly explain the steps taken in order to obtain the answer to a problem.” This teacher’s reflection on the seamless nature with which one must “explain the steps” to get “the answer” aligns with the instrumentalist characteristics of steps and a single answer as well as the mastery narrative that splits and subordinates those who put effort into their problem solving from those who are able to obtain correct answers with minimal effort. Another teacher echoed this idea, stating that mathematical knowledge is the ability “to comprehend mathematical algorithms and execute mathematical procedures.”

Others showed evidence of instrumentalist beliefs by commenting on mathematical knowledge as something that is transmitted from teachers to students through instruction and modeling. Here the emphasis is on the method of instruction, implying that students are able to master mathematics when the teacher leverages a *gradual release* model of instruction. One student described “knowing how to complete math tasks after having been taught the math topic, math skill, and applying it to any given situation or place.”

When asked about times they have been seen as “good” at mathematics, teachers primarily described their prior experiences as K12 students of mathematics. An instrumentalist belief of being “good” at math often emerged through reflections describing experiences where the teachers felt successful with solving problems based on “memorizing the steps” and applying them to a math problem to get a correct answer. Like the quote above about the transmission of knowledge from teacher to student, another teacher advanced this narrative by equating being good at math with the ability “to observe a problem being solved once, and then [to] independently and effectively complete another instance of it.” This teacher believed herself to be good at mathematics because “all [she] needed was one example” and then she was able to recreate the steps and solve additional problems using the same process.

Other participants' described memory and retention of concepts after initial learning as important to feeling a sense of competence. For example, another participant noted "once I learn a concept I don't forget it" and a participant shared, "I did not struggle to grasp concepts and I required very little to no extra practice outside of what was done in class and assigned as homework." These quotes demonstrate how the notion of speed included both the ability to solve problems quickly and the ability to learn mathematical algorithms quickly. Speed, then, emerged as an essential characteristic for viewing oneself as good at math. While the ability to memorize steps and procedures was as an indicator of mathematical proficiency, the inability to memorize steps and procedures made some teachers feel unsuccessful and discouraged. One teacher stated, "I do not see myself as someone who can rattle out facts or blurt out an answer to a math-related question in .2 seconds, or even do math quickly in my head (these are all the normal things someone has said you need to do in order to be good at math)." This idea that mathematics is a preset sequence of steps that should be completed quickly and without error came up in several reflections and is indicative of the instrumentalist belief about the nature of mathematics.

Platonist belief

Fewer teachers (18 out of 104) indicated a belief in a conception of mathematics as more open than those expressing an instrumentalist view. Four teachers defined mathematical knowledge as conceptual understanding leaning toward less rigid problem solving than the instrumentalist view. One participant's response to "What counts as mathematical knowledge?" is representative of the types of Platonist views we saw in the reflections:

Recognizing, exploring, manipulating numbers - really understanding numbers and the concepts related to them. For instance, understanding addition, subtraction, multiplication and division. Having a great sense of numbers and how to use them... If you really understand how numbers work together, you have great mathematical knowledge.

The teachers whose reflections fell into this category indicated that their thinking is more aligned with Platonist beliefs in the nature of mathematics. This quote, and the others that were similar to it, demonstrate the belief that math is more than just rules and procedures, but is still restricted to a "unified and unchanging body of knowledge" (Ernest, 1989, p. 10). Several teachers wrote about the importance of using mathematics to solve real-world problems. One teacher stated that mathematics was "the understanding and use of numbers and symbols, and how we can incorporate them into everyday life." While this teacher connected mathematics and "real life," implicit in this statement is that mathematics is a contained body of knowledge to be learned and applied in everyday situations. Furthermore, the reflections that represented a primarily Platonist view still held mathematics as an individual endeavor. One who was good at math was good because of individual success in applying mathematics in everyday situations and not for divergent or communal thinking.

When asked about times they have been seen as "good" at mathematics, teachers who demonstrated ideas aligned to Platonist beliefs made comments related to understanding math conceptually and to fluently applying given procedures. One teacher stated,

My interest peaked for math when I got to high school because I had a teacher I understood; and that is when my light bulb came on! I began to understand the concepts and rules as to why certain problems were done a particular way.

This description of understanding the “why” behind the algorithmic processes appeared in others’ reflections as reasons those individuals felt they were good at math. Understanding the “why” for certain processes also appeared in some reflections as a tension that emerged when a participant made good grades in mathematics despite sometimes struggling “to explain [the math] every time.” The teachers who held Platonist views understood that being “good” at math was not indicated solely by their recitation of mathematical facts and steps, it also included understanding the predetermined concepts found in the official mathematics curriculum. Teachers with a Platonist belief made it clear that the nature of math extended beyond memorizing facts and algorithms, but they still attended to an understanding that math “is factual and most of the time there is an exact answer.”

Problem-solving belief

While 11 of the 104 excerpts mentioned “solving problems” or “problem-solving,” there was little to no indication that these remarks extended to a belief aligned with Ernest’s (1989) “dynamic, problem-driven view of mathematics as a continually expanding field of human inquiry” (p. 21). In order to meet the criteria for a problem-solving view aligned with Ernest there would need to be evidence in the excerpt of a belief in the nature of mathematics as truly dynamic and ever-changing or evolving based on new ideas. We did not count an excerpt as problem-solving simple for the use of that language, as teachers’ views of what counts as problem solving varies widely from completing word problems on a worksheet to the dynamic problem solving to which Ernest alludes. For example, the following excerpt from a participant begins with ideas that sound as though they are aligned with this more dynamic view, but the participant returns to mastery as the end goal in the middle of the quote.

Mathematics, to me, is the ability to solve real-world, application-based questions using strategies that best work for you. I believe there is no one way to do math, and we shouldn't restrict the kids or anyone to a set way of solving a problem. I tell my students every day that anyone can do anything that they put their minds to. You just have to practice that craft to get better at it. So anyone, in my eyes, can do math. I have students who still struggle with understanding math, even with a lot of effort behind it. I just express to them that they have to work a little harder to get the concept, but it will come to them. Patience is key.

As the excerpt continues beyond the idea that “there is no one way to do math,” the participant shifts on the continuum to a less dynamic view when stating, “You just have to practice the craft to get better at it.” This statement suggests that this teacher still believes mathematics to be something that can be mastered with dedicated time and effort—both hallmarks underpinning a larger meritocratic narrative. While the teacher may espouse to a problem-solving belief in the nature of mathematics, there are instrumentalist beliefs that interfere or undermine that belief. The following excerpt from another participant demonstrates a view more aligned with the problem-solving perspective.

I love that there are several strategies that can be used to solve the same problem. It makes it so people can solve problems in the way that they feel most comfortable. This is another thing I love about teaching math. I love that I can empower my students by saying you can use whatever strategy works best for you!

It is evident that this participant believes in the value of empowering students to use “several strategies to solve the same problem.” It is difficult to tell from this quote whether the teacher shows the students a set of strategies first and then lets them choose which to use (instrumentalist view) or presents tasks to students and supports their exploration of possible strategies to solve it which is aligned with Ernest’s problem-solving belief that “math is a man-made creation that is continually expanding” (1989, p. 10).

External perceptions

Beyond the three types of belief, we coded to trace when and by whom participants had been seen as good at mathematics. When asked to reflect on the question, “Have you been seen by others (or yourself) as ‘good’ at mathematics?,” several participants described others’ perceptions of them as “good” at mathematics and how that played a role in shaping their beliefs about mathematical knowledge and their own abilities. Similar to reflections described in the previous section, where participants cited their grades and test scores as markers of mastery, 11 of 31 responses reported that the praises, opinions, and mathematics-related requests from other people had some influence on their beliefs. Six participants mentioned some form of the statement, “other people have always said that I was good at math.” These participants have memories of having the “good at math” label bestowed upon them by other individuals. Participants referenced their peers (e.g., “many of my peers in school believed I was good at math”), their teachers and professors (e.g., “Teachers encouraged me, provided engaging manipulatives, and thought I was excellent”), and family (e.g., “Yes, I must say that my family and colleagues often make comments about my math knowledge”). One participant shared,

When thinking about my experience with mathematics in middle and high school, I can only remember being that person everyone went to for math help because I was Asian. Every student and teacher believed I was intelligent and good at math because of my ethnicity, not because I struggled and figured out what I was doing just like everyone else.

This participant’s experience with model minority bias (Martin, 2009, p. 216) navigating perceptions of others based on her ethnicity did not appear to change the way she viewed herself or her mathematical abilities, but it supports the pervasive narrative that there are people (and in this case, people of certain ethnicities) who are “math people.” Participants described “math people” as inherently better at mathematics than others. In these instances, mathematical skill is viewed as a fixed attribute of some people akin to a genetic, inherited, and immutable trait. The characteristics that make one recognizable as “good at math” align with measurable, quantifiable, aspects of mathematical knowledge, fluency, speed, accuracy. In addition, their permanence in these positions aligns with the characteristic of mastery that the identity persists over time. Math people would always be good at math, but non-math people were forever limited in their mathematical abilities. Another participant echoed this notion, stating, “I always considered myself somewhat of a ‘math’ person who comes from a long lineage of math people. I wasn’t as math-oriented as my parents and sister, but I did well in math and enjoyed my math classes.”

Beyond the praises and compliments routinely received about their perceived mastery of mathematics, participant responses revealed that being called upon to assist others with mathematics tasks was another reflection of how the world viewed their competence. One participant stated, “I was the student that everyone would come to for help when we were given different assignments or had a test coming up.” Another shared, “Many of my peers in school believed I was good at math. Often, they would ask me to tutor them on something that they were confused about on an assignment.” While the perception of being someone who is good enough

at mathematics to be able to assist others may, in effect, boost the self-confidence of an individual, that perception is deeply rooted in the mastery narratives described throughout this paper and is often a result of compliance to the narrowly focused definition of being “good at math” reinforced through the U.S. education system’s hyper-focus on grades and test scores. The participants who were viewed as “math people,” due to high scores on mathematics tasks and exams, were then called upon to assist others in obtaining high scores to demonstrate a transfer of “mastery.”

Resonances of Mastery Narratives across Data that Glows

While in the above section, we discussed data coded to Ernest’s framework, there were other experts that glowed outside of our coding schema. MacLure (2013) described data that glows as having an intensity or resonance that opens space for wonder, curiosity, or even disgust. These excerpts do not have quantitative power, yet they were sticky for our data-researcher-theory intra-action. The first of these was speed and pressure to attend to a particular predetermined rhythm of teaching. One teacher reflected,

I do have an opinion that the standards shouldn't be pushed so fast, though. My students do not have time to master one standard before moving on to the next. We also have so many math standards to teach that I think we should focus more on mastering addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division by the end of elementary school. I have many students who come into fourth [grade] not knowing how to add and subtract. They also don't know their multiplication facts which makes it harder to teach the next step. They are made to memorize their multiplication facts instead of being taught strategies to figure it out, even if they don't have them memorized. All in all, I have a lot of students who don't have confidence in math because of the pressure of all the standards and the pacing.

While advocating for the opportunity to slow down, this participant also reinforced the timelines for her students to master a set of skills that will lead to success by lamenting what they do not know by the time they get to fourth grade.

A second glowing data set pointed to external sources of reinforcement of mastery narratives. One of those sources was feedback the teachers (as students) received throughout their K-12 education experience in the form of mathematics grades and standardized examination scores. Ten reflections mentioned high test scores and grades as markers of being good at mathematics. When teachers wrote about times they felt successful with mathematics, memories they discussed were linked to “perform[ing] well on mathematics exams” and “receiv[ing] the highest letter grade.” In fact, one teacher stated, “My senior year of high school I completed math with a 99% in a regular-ed math class, and I finally felt I was good at math.” Another wrote,

I didn't know or was confident that I was good at math until I was in eighth grade. My math teacher pointed out to me that I was good at math due to the fact I was passing all my quizzes and tests. At that moment, I started to know that I was good at math and needed to be more confident about what I know.

Both participants relied the reassurance of high grades to believe in themselves as being good at math. The high grades were most likely a result of mastering a set of facts or procedures. In response to our question: Where are the qualities of mastery showing up or escaping notice in and around mathematics classrooms? throughout the reflections, we noted a consistent adherence to mastery narratives about mathematics across the participants. The participants spoke about the ways being good at mathematics was bounded by measurable outcomes—grades, test scores, speed,

and accuracy. We also noted that the participants viewed the subject of mathematics as bounded—math was held as neutral and outside of social construction. We find it important to linger with the question of what mastery narratives are producing in mathematics classrooms and the grim futures that are written when mathematics is held off from students who do not demonstrate early indications of mastery. Reading across these two columns, we see how the qualities of mastery are allowed to fester in K12 mathematics classrooms and turn to our other two questions: What kinds of communities might build and sustain teachers and researchers in transforming a culture of exclusion? What bids and negotiations might foster more joyful, curious, and creative mathematical classrooms? We turn to these in the re-envisioning.

Re-envisioning

In questioning the persistence of mastery, Singh (2018) emphasized mastery not as something to overcome, but as an emerging inheritance that we “might (yet) survive” (p. 2). She suggested, borrowing Donna Haraway’s (2016) phrase that we “‘stay with the trouble’ that is produced through attention to where, how, between whom and toward what futures mastery is engaged” (p. 2). We have deep concerns about how, where, and between whom the qualities of mastery are emerging in order to pursue progress in the context of schools.

We have attended to our first research question, Where are the qualities of mastery showing up or escaping notice in and around mathematics classrooms?, in the previous sections. While pointing out the pervasiveness of mastery narratives in mathematics education is valuable, Singh asserted that unthinking mastery is a task that is impossible yet “profoundly hopeful one that gazes toward a future it still cannot see” (p. 21). Ohsiek (2023) has questioned the underlying premises for improvements in mathematics education that focus on improving society and financial stability. She wonders, “What if we taught mathematics with the goal of sharing joy and wonder, not to improve a student’s chance at earning six figures in the future?” (p. 8). Therefore, we turn to our remaining research questions: What kinds of communities might build and sustain teachers and researchers in transforming a culture of exclusion? What bids and negotiations might foster more joyful, curious, and creative mathematical classrooms?

Fig. 4. Aligning Ernest’s problem-solving view of mathematics and Living Mathematx

To begin to answer this, we turn to Gutiérrez (2023) who draws on Tuck's (2009) desire-based research. Desire-based research acknowledges loss and suffering of communities and simultaneously recognizes the desire or longing for different visions and futures. This research acknowledges contradiction and intersectionality and is future focused. In our collective work with teachers, we have seen, heard, and felt their desires for other futures. We have witnessed as their values have been compromised and the desire for resurgence of the joy they (once) found in teaching and doing mathematics with children. Therefore, here we co-construct responses to the qualities of mastery, drawing on Gutiérrez' (2017) living mathematx, her vision for practicing a mathematics that points our attention toward survival and joy. She proposes that we consider the nature of mathematics, as Ernest's framework supports us in doing, and the ethics of mathematical teaching and learning, and importantly- how we are affected by it, as Singh's qualities of mastery help to elucidate. We invite other mathematics education researchers and mathematics teacher educators to desire with us different futures. We begin with splitting.

Splitting, the first quality of mastery, divides and creates boundaries and binaries. To reimagine and disrupt this bifurcation which opens the door to subordination, we point to both-and thinking. In both-and thinking multiple, and even conflicting ideas can be held and seen as valid and valuable. What if students were invited by their teachers to engage in problem-solving in creative and joyful ways? What if their curiosity was centered and they were supported in considering the multiple and various ways that problems can be solved? What if they were engaged in holding their ideas and another's as equal of careful consideration and listening? What if the desire for *correctness* was replaced with a desire for an ongoing ethical *rightness* in relation? What if we centered mathematx (Gutiérrez, 2017) as a means of survival and joy? We imagine a future/present where teachers are in caring relation with students and more-than-human others and those relations are not structured and predicated by test scores, rankings, and red, yellow, green splitting and subordination. This requires a hard re-set in our adherence and allegiance to testing companies, digital learning platforms, and curriculum maps and learning trajectories (Cannon et al., in press; Myers, 2022).

In place of subordination, we offer, interdependence, "recognizing our responsibilities, putting ourselves back together again in relation to others and the worlds in which we participate, and doing this work collectively are at the heart of spirituality" (Gutiérrez, 2022, p. 381). We wonder, what if instead of separating and tracking students, an academic apartheid (Aguirre, 2025) with "high" students in one track and "low" students in another, we recognized our collective responsibility for the ongoing education of our community? What if we privileged collaboration over competition? What if we acknowledged on ongoing and elaborate interdependence? One of our research team members, who attended an Islamic school, shared her surprise at the staunch individualism and competitiveness noted in the participants' reflections. She shared that in her school, teachers expected students to work in community with one another and to offer peer support when their classmates did not understand something. There was a sense of community, a we-are-better-togetherness that permeated her school experiences. We reimagine and advocate for communities in and around mathematical problems. This is not the same as a teacher assigning a "high flier" to help a low student, but an engagement and curiosity in each other's mathematical ideas. In place the staunch independence that is encouraged by subordinations, we point to a vision of mathematics classrooms that value interconnectedness, reciprocity, and interdependence (Gutiérrez, 2017). We imagine classrooms where teachers and students listen with curiosity to each others' ideas for the purpose of communal growth. We follow Ahmed (2013) in recognizing that our discomfort with the "available scripts for living and loving" might lead toward "other (perhaps no less discomfoting) possibilities for collective life" (Ahmed, 2013, p. 425). Gutiérrez (2017)

asked, “Can we come to understand mathematics as a living practice that needs actors and can respond to their needs? (p. 9). As another of our team members said,

I didn't realize teaching math with middle schoolers could incite joy until I embraced joy as my way of teaching. Bringing in joy—stickers, high-five Friday, “on Thursdays we wear joggers”, accepting the dare, number talks, and “convince me that”—made the math classroom a place to be joyful, and in feeling joy, it made math joyful, and it made math communal, which made it learnable. (Erica)

Until we can unearth the damaging taken-for-granted practices in school mathematics that perpetuate mastery narratives, we will continue to see the persistence of the splitting and subordination of children and the persistence of those positions in their lives over time. We will continue to have students and parents enter our classrooms proclaiming that they are not good at math until we reimagine and put into place other practices that affirm interdependence, both-and thinking, and aesthetics, joy, and messiness. Martin (2015) asked of NCTM's *Principles to Actions* document, “Does this document represent, symbolically and in spirit, the kind of disruptive violence to the status quo that can move the last to first?” (p. 22). If we were to ask ourselves this question, we know that the suggestions we have offered in this paper (many of which have been levied by others) are not enough. And yet, we think that these questions need to continue to be asked and taken-for-granted assumptions called out. We perpetuate hope in the both/and of creating possibilities for more humanizing becomings within school mathematics while understanding that the systemic culture of exclusion (Louie, 2017) constrains possibilities.

Singh (2018) stated that we “engage education as praxis, as a process of critical becoming that entails various (and at times totally unforeseeable) forms of *care* and practices of *unlearning* that which we already ‘know’” (p. 67, italics ours). The authors of this paper, and many teachers we have worked with, grew up engaged with an instrumentalist view of mathematics with clear right or wrong answers, problem sets with answers to odd problems in the back, and the teacher as the holder of the processes for doing mathematics (a set of routines and procedures). Therefore, we and many of the teachers we work with have had to unlearn this as the only way to do school mathematics and consider how to become otherwise as mathematics teachers and teacher educators. A problem-solving view of mathematics provides “new possibilities for nonmasterful relations” (Singh, 2017, p. 174-175).

Even just recognizing that there are other possibilities of what school mathematics could be, opens up possibilities. A problem-solving view of mathematics could disrupt the pursuit of progress that Llewellyn (2016) described. Teachers holding and maintaining a problem-solving view of mathematics would be in constant negotiation with the norms and discourses around progress that define the *normal* mathematical child. The ways that teachers may want to be in mathematics classrooms is entangled with and hindered by discourses that center what is measurable, countable, and containable in mathematics. Therefore, holding the problem-solving perspective requires one to engage in mathematics in deviant ways. As a result, teachers and teacher educators who take up this view find themselves scraping against boundaries drawn by the limits of what counts as progress in school mathematics. Yet, a problem-solving view with its tolerance for indeterminacy would make splitting and subordination more cumbersome. What if we looked for the beauty in mathematical thinking, the joy of an aha moment, the pleasure in puzzling over a challenging problem? What conditions might make that event possible. Given Singh's orientation toward education as a critical becoming, the problem-solving view has the most potential for decolonized mathematics. Both the instrumentalist and the Platonist view require anticipatable

responses as the body of knowledge is static and unchanging. What forms of care might we offer our students and ourselves in order to unlearn our attachments to instrumentalist forms of mathematical teaching and learning?

Afterword: Dialogue Between Scholars

This project was about pushing back against mastery. It may seem anachronistic to push back against a word that, admittedly, has violent origins, but that in 2025 is more commonly used to mean something far less tragic and violent. What is wrong with pursuing mastery? Is it not simply the pursuit of advanced knowledge, deeper thinking, new discoveries? As we shared in the writing of this paper, these thoughts often surfaced. In a practical sense, shifting our language isn't likely to be enough to compel us to change our practices, especially when those practices are so deeply believed to be good or at the very least neutral. This very thought worked in us to make us believe that the little things don't matter or that we can cultivate joy in our math classrooms without attending to the minutiae of language. How is any of this practical, anyway? What difference will this make to the third-grade teacher who is just trying to get through the standards so that her young students can do the best they can on the test at the end of the year? But despite these rising doubts, we came to believe that it is in attending to these very linkages where we may pry the door open for deeper examination. It is through that crack, where joy may enter in.

In writing this manuscript, we grappled with the practicality of this journey, but ultimately, we finished the project. Brittney moved across the country and out of academia to work as an elementary mathematics district leader where she faced the pervasiveness of mastery networks at all levels, but has continued to push for the reframing of math classrooms as joyful and inclusive spaces. Erica graduated with her doctoral degree and began a position writing curriculum for the Boys and Girls Clubs of America. Susan changed universities and her grant was threatened for including the word equity in the title. Merlong worked to finish her degree while working full time in the classroom and navigating personal and family losses. We each had different and intermittent periods of continuing to write into this paper as Juan M. Gerardo, our open reviewer, provided feedback, encouragement, and thoughtful critique. Through our interactions with Juan, we almost completely reorganized the paper, removed one theoretical framework and played with formatting. The formatting changes came when Juan saw some of Susan's other work (Cannon, 2019; 2020) and wondered why she did not experiment in those ways here. Why didn't she? I, Susan, had been disciplined and conformed herself to certain expectations of what *mathematics education research* could and should look like—straightforward, empirical, rational, following the guidelines and rules, while also pushing back and trying to make space for different ways of being in mathematics education (Cannon, 2020a; 2020b). Within the field of qualitative inquiry, I felt free to play and experiment with writing conventions, form, and texture, taking academic joyrides (Cannon & Holbrook, 2020) and playing with the excess in writing processes (Cannon & Cross, 2020). Despite this journal's clear statement that authors are “especially encouraged to ‘push the boundaries’ of mathematics education when writing, in terms of theory, methods, conception, and presentation” (JTMME, para 1), we uploaded a linear straightforward manuscript in our initial submission. Somehow, as lead author, I still did not feel that I was allowed (It did not even cross my mind) to play with form in mathematics education research spaces. Yet, in his first round of feedback, Juan said to take a “choose your own adventure” approach. He gave critical feedback to clarify the relationships between Singh, Ernest, and Llewellyn which resulted in the diagrams, he asked us to recenter joy, curiosity, and creativity which we talked about in our meeting, but he did not feel in the paper, and importantly he pushed us to put ourselves into the manuscript and to consider challenging form. Juan wrote (he also mentions his communication with Alex Moore, the founding editor):

How creative / far could we push the boundaries of the analysis and narrative. Alex seemed very supportive. If this is a route that could be of interest to you, if you think this could be an approach you can take. Of course, this might inspire you to take a different route (which is fine) that will have the manuscript reflect the argument / claims you want to make.

As a result of this we added the introductory section, From Georgia, with love, and composed dialogue from teachers about students that resonated in our memories. This dialogue became a part of the two-columned sections of the paper where we tried to show as we were telling. In other words, one column provides the argument, and the other column is designed to show what that looks, sounds, feels like in the classroom.

This change in the formatting became one of our favorite features of the paper—the opportunity to encourage a diffractive reading. In a way, the formatting presents another challenge against mastery—that which academia has deemed appropriate style. Susan challenged the team to think differently and, in a way, taught us that in playing with the formatting and style we might find joy in writing this paper as we hope readers find openings toward joy in their diffractive reading toward mathematics. We owe much to Juan for helping us to stay with the trouble of this paper through over a year of revisions, illnesses, injuries, job changes, promotions, graduations, dissertation submissions, and geographical relocations. And yet, even as we sit with the trouble of mastery for an extended period, we are left with more questions than answers. As Erica reflected recently, despite all our work, when her son got off the bus and shared that he had the highest growth in his class on the MAP math assessment, she was proud and still yearns for him to develop a “good at math” identity, because in this world, that still matters. We hope that we’ve pulled a thread that leads to an unravelling but are humbled by the conditions of our world into which we send this work. We engage in “wake work” (Sharpe, 2016) to bring to consciousness the ways mathematics has been yet another space that has been colonized and lies in the wake of a history of entitled masters laying claim on land, bodies, livingness. It is indeed, very “woke” of us to call mastery, individualism, and the very notion of merit into question. But as we begin to see mastery, and thus merit, as an inheritance arbitrarily granted to one, but not another, we are compelled to put this paper into the world.

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